

SO₂ Instrument Description

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SO₂ measurements are made by the FAAM Airborne Laboratory using a pulsed UV fluorescence spectrometer, specifically a Thermo Fisher Scientific model TEi-43i TLE SO₂ analyser (s/n 1505564557). This instrument has been flown since 2016, and customized as described in the flow diagram below.

An external Perma Pure Multi-strand Nafion dryer (part no. PD-50T-24MPR) lowers the moisture content from the air being sampled and therefore minimises fluorescence quenching by water vapour. The dryer is plumbed using a reflux setup, which returns the dry sample back to the dryer sheath for use as the purge gas after it has gone through the detector. Since this method uses all of the dry sample as the purge gas, only the sample flow required for analysis passes through the dryer which results in high drying efficiency. The vacuum on the purge gas is provided by the analyser's internal vacuum pump.

The instrument sample flow rate was increased from approximately 0.5 to 2.0 SLPM, to reduce lag times and speed up instrumental response times. A mass flow controller (MFC3, Alicat Scientific, part no. MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON) replaces the original TEi43i glass capillary and flow sensor, to maintain constant sample mass flow rate.

Two unheated hydrocarbon kickers remove interference caused by volatile organic compounds which fluoresce at similar UV wavelengths to that of SO₂ fluorescence, and may lead to a false SO₂ amount fraction. The second HC kicker was plumbed in parallel to improve sample flow conductance to the fluorescence cell, to cope with the higher sample mass flow rate, a method first described in Ryerson et al (1998).

Following this initial customisation in 2016, laboratory experimental characterisation for temperature and pressure changes demonstrated a significant increase in instrumental drift, in particular background/baseline signal, which were linked to the instrument manufacturer's pressure and temperature compensation algorithms. These compensation algorithms were therefore disabled, but did not entirely suppress the detector baseline drift.

In order to monitor and correct for baseline drift, frequent (~10 to 15 mins interval) 'zero' calibrations are performed by passing the air sample through an external zero air scrubber cartridge filled with activated charcoal (as used in Teledyne-API model T100 UV fluorescence SO₂ analyser). A three-way electro-solenoid valve (eValve 7, Parker-Hannifin series 9, part number 009-0294-900) allows the detector to sample a SO₂-free matrix for a set time (45 sec). When performed regularly in-flight, mean amount fraction can be calculated for each in-flight 'zero'. Mean 'zeros' are then linearly interpolated to provide a drift-corrected baseline, which can be subtracted from the raw amount fraction, before being scaled using the detector sensitivity.

A 2 µm particulate filter (Swagelok part no. SS-4FW-2) downstream of the scrubber cartridge protects the TEi43i internal plumbing (e.g. fluorescence cell, optic lenses...) from potential contamination, for instance from activated charcoal dust during zeroing.

Sample inlet and instrument response

From 2012 to 2021, a rear-ward facing ½" OD stainless steel (SS) tube, mounted on a blank BAe-146 aircraft Aluminium window, served as inlet for the TEi43i. The SS tube ID was lined with a ⅜" OD PFA Teflon tube, to accommodate simultaneous atmospheric sampling of ozone, sulphur dioxide and carbon monoxide.

Since 2021, a new pressure-building trace gas inlet has replaced the rear-ward facing inlet. This inlet was initially designed by Richard J. McLaughlin, an instrument design and fabrication specialist at NOAA's Chemical Sciences Division, for NASA's Douglas DC8 (e.g. ATom-2 missions) and NOAA's Lockheed WP-3D Orion aircrafts. The inlet design was first adapted to interface with our aircraft windows by Chris Reed at FAAM in 2019, for use as a fast NO_x measurements inlet.

The new core chemistry McLaughlin inlet is located on starboard windows no. 11 or 12 depending on the cabin configuration (i.e. ~12 to 13 m from the nose of the aircraft). The

picture below illustrates the pylon/shroud inlet mounted on window no. 11 (nose of aircraft to the RHS of picture).

Two of the three inlet internal ports within the pylon are lined with 1/4" OD PFA Teflon tubes, then teed to a single 3/8" OD PFA Teflon tube.

Ambient air is drawn into the aircraft cabin through the 3/8" OD Teflon tube using an all-PTFE Teflon double-headed sample pump (KNF part no. N834.3 FTE). The sample flow (~25 SLPM near surface, degrading to ~ 7 SLPM at 35000') passes through a two-way, normally open, electro-solenoid valve (eValve5, Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-2414-213), used to seal the inlet during pre-flight preparations.

The operation of the KNF sample pump and eValve 5 is automated by the aircraft weight-on-wheels signal; ambient air sampling starts as soon as the aircraft is airborne. This arrangement minimises instrument inlet contamination by airfield polluted air, such as during engines start with aircraft parked on stand, or while taxiing for take-off.

The air sample is transferred to a 3/8" to 1/4" Teflon tee piece (Entegris/Galtek part no part# UT4-6-4N); a short length 1/4" od Teflon tubing connects the tee piece to the TEi43i instrument Nafion dryer.

The excess flow provided by the KNF sample pump is directed to a PFA Teflon buffer volume (PFAVOL) constructed out of three 1 1/2" MNPT 120 mL column segments (Saville part no. 500-120-02), 3/8" OD tube port closures (Saville part no. 600-058-19), and female connectors (Saville part no. 730-0502). The buffer volume is used to dampen oscillating flow effects caused by the KNF sample pump (double diaphragm pressure pulses).

Besides the sequenced in-flight zeroing, a further instrument baseline check can be performed pre- and post-flight using a second external, larger capacity (500 mL), scrubber cartridge (Cole Parmer part no. 01418-50) equipped with in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4) and 5 μm PTFE membrane. This scrubber cartridge is half-filled with potassium permanganate coated

alumina spheres (Sofnofil, from Molecular Products Ltd), and activated charcoal, for the removal of NO_x, O₃ and SO₂. During the preparatory phase on the ground, the KNF sample pump is off, cabin air can pass through this larger scrubber cartridge by actuating the three-way electro-solenoid eValve 6 (Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-3414-213), so SO₂-scrubbed cabin air can be sampled by the TEi43i instrument.

During flight, the overflow from the KNF sample pump is constantly monitored by a microbridge mass airflow sensor (MFM, Honeywell model AWM5104VN, 0-20 SLPM), to ensure cabin air is not inadvertently sampled, especially when the inlet pumping performance decreases while approaching our flight ceiling altitude (30000-35000 feet).

The above sampling inlet arrangement enables the TEi43i spectrometer to work within its operating pressure limits, with its inlet pressure effectively following the aircraft cabin pressure.

Based on the current inlet configuration, the instrument lag time (initial signal rise detection) is estimated to be $\sim 4 \pm 1$ sec. The T90 instrumental time response was determined as 18 sec. Please note that no correction for lag time has been applied to our submitted data timestamps.

Calibration and reference scale traceability

The TEi43i analyser is regularly calibrated in FAAM's laboratories or the University of York's [COZI laboratory](#), part of the Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories, over the range 0-1000 nmol/mol [ppb].

FAAM's SO₂ in synthetic air surveillance standard gases are procured from BOC Ltd, material number 154578-AK-S. Specifically, the standard consists of a Spectra-Seal (BOC proprietary passivated, stability assured for 5 years), size AK, 40 litres, aluminium cylinder. Its certified SO₂ mole fraction has an uncertainty ≤ 5%, determined by BOC's UKAS-accredited (ISO/IEC 17025:2017) calibration laboratory, using reference standards traceable to the UK National Physical Laboratory SO₂ gravimetric scale.

A multi-point calibration is performed by dynamically diluting (with mass flow controllers) the calibration gas mixture of SO₂/Air overflowing the instrument inlet, to determine the SO₂ sensitivity of the fluorescence detector.

When combined with the drift-corrected baseline (linearly interpolated zeros), the SO₂ mole fraction can be scaled using the detector sensitivity with the following equation:

$$\text{Mole fraction [ppb]} = \frac{\text{raw_signal [ppb]} - \text{interpolated_baseline [ppb]}}{\text{Sensitivity [ppb/ppb]}}$$

Measurement uncertainty

The uncertainty of the detector sensitivity is estimated at ±6% (multi-point calibration curve slope), plus an additional ±3% (uncertainty of dynamic dilution system), giving an overall uncertainty of ±9%. The minimum uncertainty is estimated as ±3 ppb based on the interpolated zero uncertainty.

Fluorescence interferences by Nitric Oxide

SO₂ data submitted for the FAAM's TEi43i s/n 1505564557 is not corrected for fluorescence interferences from nitric oxide commonly encountered during sampling of undiluted combustion exhaust.

Nitric oxide interference tests were performed in the FAAM laboratories on 31/07/2025 and 05/12/2025 by dynamically diluting (with mass flow controllers) a 5080 ppb NO in nitrogen mixture (BOC material number 178150-AH-V, alpha-volumetric standard, cylinder number 153837SG) in synthetic 'zero' air (BOC material number 122944-L-C, BTCA-178 grade).

Apparent SO₂ mole fractions (due to fluorescing nitric oxide) were plotted against diluted NO mole fractions, and the interference equation was determined by an orthogonal distance regression (ODR) fit, weighting apparent mean SO₂ mole fractions by their 1 σ standard deviations, and mean NO mole fractions by their combined [k=1] uncertainties from dynamic dilution.

NO fluorescence interference test results from 31/07/2025

NO fluorescence interference test results from 5/12/2025

Both tests yielded comparable results. We recommend employing the equation obtained for the 5/12/2025 experiment which was conducted when the TEi43i analyser was conditioned for a period of time comparable to a pre-flight (minimum 2 hours).

Fluorescence interferences by BTEX and aromatic hydrocarbons

The FAAM-customised TEi43i analyser employs two HC-kickers in parallel to maintain good flow conductance to its fluorescence cell.

We evaluated the HC-kickers removal efficiency and potential interference from BTEX/aromatic hydrocarbons by sampling a mixture of aromatic hydrocarbons in nitrogen (total mole fraction > 4 ppm), provided by the University of York Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories.

Compound	Mole fraction, nmol/mol
Benzene	882.774
Toluene	483.093
Ethylbenzene	546.221
m-Xylene	654.575
p-Xylene	416.518
o-Xylene	424.308
1,3,5 trimethylbenzene	357.136
1,2,4 trimethylbenzene	304.103
1,2,3 trimethylbenzene	282.235
Total	4350.963

10 Litres Luxfer cylinder number D860619 composition (James Hopkins, University of York, NCAS, personal communication, 11/12/2025)

At these high hydrocarbon mole fractions, we found evidence of fluorescence interferences, which we are still in the process of quantifying at this time of writing.

A critical diagnostics parameter of the TEi431 analyser (pulsed UV lamp voltage) was found to correlate with the HC interference, likely related to the interfering fluorescence affecting the lamp stability feedback control. This diagnostic parameter is now used to flag SO₂ data for potential HC interference.

References

T. B. Ryerson, M. P. Buhr, G. J. Frost, P. D. Goldan, J. S. Holloway, G. Hubler, B. T. Jobson, W. C. Kuster, S. A. McKeen, D. D. Parrish, J. M. Roberts, D. T. Sueper, M. Trainer, J. Williams and F. C. Fehsenfeld, *Journal of Geophysical Research-Atmospheres*, 1998, 103, 22569-22583.